

THE IMPACT OF FINTECH APPLICATION IMPLEMENTATION ON IMPROVING CONSUMER CREDIT RATINGS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the impact of fintech applications (FA) on credit ratings (CR). It examines the functional capabilities of various fintech tools, such as personal finance management apps, monitoring services, and digital lending platforms, and their role in ensuring the accessibility of financial services. Using specific applications like CreditKarma, Mint by Intuit, and SoFi as examples, the significance of FA in shaping the financial literacy of the population is emphasized. It is highlighted that the development of FA is a complex and multi-stage process that requires the implementation of a significant list of features and ensuring a high level of information security.

Keywords: Fintech applications, credit ratings, financial literacy, personal finance management, digital lending platforms, financial services accessibility.

Introduction

The financial industry is currently undergoing a significant transformation due to the rapid growth of financial technology. This evolution is characterized by the integration of advanced technology into traditional financial services, notably through the development and adoption of fintech applications (FA). These digital tools are not just changing the way financial transactions are conducted, but also affecting consumers' credit ratings (CR). According to the forecast of Research and Markets (Dublin, Ireland), the global financial technology market will reach \$225.1 billion by 2027, increasing by an average of 12.9 % [1].

CR serving as a pivotal metric for financial institutions, determine the creditworthiness of individuals and play a critical role in their ability to access mortgages, and other financial products. Traditionally, these ratings have been influenced by factors such as repayment history, debt levels, and credit history length. However, with the advent of FA, there is a growing discourse on how these digital solutions are influencing

these traditional metrics and potentially enhancing the CR of consumers.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of the introduction of FA on improving consumer CR. The article discusses the functionality of various fintech tools, such as personal finance management applications, credit rating monitoring services and digital lending platforms.

Main part

Fintech applications (FA), a term that encapsulates a range of digital tools and platforms in the realm of financial technology, have emerged as pivotal components in the modern financial ecosystem. These applications are defined by their use of advanced technological solutions to deliver financial services, ranging from payment processing to personal financial management and investment advising. Their core characteristics are the fusion of technology with traditional financial services to enhance accessibility, efficiency, and user experience. According to a Statista study, the United States became the leader in the global fintech market in 2023 (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The number of companies with an estimated value of \$1 billion or more in different countries, 2023 [2]

The impact of FA on users' lives is profound and multifaceted. They have democratized access to financial services, allowing individuals from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds to engage in financial activities that were previously out of reach. Fintech tools have simplified complex financial processes, making them more understandable and manageable for the average consumer. The scope of these applications extends be-

yond mere transactional capabilities; they are instrumental in shaping financial behavior, promoting financial literacy, and fostering a more inclusive financial environment.

Types and functions of FA. Initially, the term "fintech" applied broadly to the technology employed at the back-end systems of established financial institutions. However, since the global financial crisis of 2008, fintech has evolved to reshape the way money is

managed, shifting from institutional to consumer-focused services.

FA continue to evolve, driven by technological advancements and changing consumer needs. They are not only making financial services more accessible and convenient but also democratizing the financial landscape, allowing users to have more control over their financial decisions and data. The ongoing development of fintech is poised to further transform the financial sector, promising more innovative solutions and reshaping the global economy.

FA represent a broad spectrum of digital solutions designed to address various aspects of financial management and operations. These applications are characterized by their unique functionalities, targeting different financial needs and preferences of consumers. The following table 1 categorizes FA into distinct types, highlighting their key functionalities and how they cater to specific financial activities. This classification aids in understanding the diverse nature of fintech solutions and their specific roles in the financial ecosystem.

Table 1.

Types of FA and their characteristics.

Type of FA	Functionality	Target user	Impact on financial management
Digital wallets and payment apps	Facilitate online and offline transactions	General consumers.	Accelerate safe transactions globally, shifting consumer preferences from traditional to electronic payment methods.
Personal finance management tools.	Budgeting, expense tracking, financial planning.	Individuals seeking financial organization.	Aid in organizing and optimizing personal finances, fostering financial discipline and informed decision-making.
Investment and trading platforms.	Access to stock markets, portfolio management.	Novice and experienced investors.	Democratize investment opportunities, educate on financial markets.
Peer-to-peer lending platforms	Connect borrowers and lenders, facilitate loans	Borrowers and investors.	Provide alternative lending and investment opportunities.

The table illustrates the multifaceted nature of FA, each serving distinct functions and catering to varied consumer needs. Collectively, these applications significantly contribute to enhancing financial accessibility, literacy, and empowerment among users, reflecting the transformative impact of fintech in the domain of personal and communal financial management. According to the forecast of the international consulting company deVere Group, in 2024, the main trends in the field of fintech will be the growing importance of cryptocurrencies, the spread of digital currencies of central banks (CBDC), the introduction of AI, the growing demand for mobile payments, cybersecurity and global financial accessibility [3]. Increased access to financial services, especially in developing regions, can contribute to poverty reduction and the development of economic opportunities on a global scale.

CR and their importance. CR a crucial aspect of the financial sector, are an assessment of the creditworthiness of individuals and entities. These ratings, often represented as scores, are determined by credit bureaus based on a range of financial factors. The requirements for a good CR typically include a history of timely payments, the length of credit history, the types of credit used, and the amount of debt relative to credit limits.

According to the Federal Reserve System report, credit card debt in the United States in 2023 amounted to \$1.13 trillion. The delinquency rate on all types of consumer debt, except for student loans, also increased in the last quarter of 2023 [4]. As of the end of December 2023, 3.1 % of the outstanding consumer debt in the United States was in delinquency.

CR plays a pivotal role in determining an individual's or entity's ability to borrow money and the terms of that borrowing, including interest rates. A high CR indicates a high likelihood of repaying loans, leading to more favorable loan terms, such as lower interest rates. Conversely, a low CR can result in higher interest rates or even denial of credit. CR also extends beyond the realm of borrowing [5]. They can affect the ability to rent housing, secure certain types of employment, and impact insurance premiums. In some regions, CR can even influence utility service agreements and cell phone contract terms.

In summary, maintaining a good CR is essential for financial stability and access to various financial opportunities. It reflects an individual's or entity's financial responsibility and reliability, impacting a wide range of financial and non-financial aspects of life.

Identifying a CR using a FA. The impact of FA on CR is a multifaceted phenomenon, reflecting the intersection of technology, finance, and consumer behavior. Fintech tools, through their innovative functionalities, have significantly altered how consumers interact with financial services, thereby influencing their creditworthiness in several ways.

Firstly, FA like personal finance management tools and budgeting apps have empowered consumers with better financial oversight [6]. These tools enable users to track their spending, set budgets, and monitor account balances in real-time. By fostering financial discipline and awareness, such applications can help users avoid late payments and manage debt more effectively, positively impacting their credit scores.

Fintech platforms, especially those involved in lending and credit scoring, often utilize alternative data for credit assessments. Traditional credit scoring models primarily rely on credit history, loan repayment records, and credit utilization ratios. However, FA may include additional factors like utility bill payments, rent payment history, and even social media behavior in their credit assessments. This broader data set can provide a more comprehensive view of a consumer's financial behavior, potentially benefiting those with limited traditional credit history. Fintech solutions in the realm of peer-to-peer lending and microfinancing have opened up new avenues for credit access. These platforms often serve individuals who are underserved by traditional banks, offering them loans based on alternative credit models.

Examples of successful FA:

- Credit Karma (Mountain View, California) provides users with free access to their credit scores and reports, along with tools for credit monitoring. This app helps users understand the factors affecting their credit score and offers personalized recommendations for improving it. By regularly monitoring their credit status, users can identify and address issues promptly, thereby maintaining or improving their CR.

- Mint by Intuit (Oakland, California) is a personal finance management tool that helps users track and manage their finances. It aggregates financial information from various sources, providing users with a comprehensive view of their financial health. By helping users stay on top of their bills, manage budgets, and monitor credit usage, Mint can indirectly contribute to maintaining or improving credit scores by encouraging responsible financial behavior.

- SoFi (San Francisco, California), initially known for student loan refinancing, now offers a range of financial products including personal loans and credit score monitoring. SoFi's credit score monitoring tool helps users track their credit score over time, providing insights into how their financial behavior affects their creditworthiness. By offering educational resources and tools, SoFi empowers users to take informed steps towards improving their credit scores.

FA development is crucial to remain competitive in the rapidly evolving financial landscape, offering users convenient and efficient ways to manage their finances, complete transactions, and access a range of financial services anytime, anywhere. The advantages of FA compared to traditional financial services include: accessibility of use, reduction of commission costs, time savings, a wide range of services, personalization [7].

Required features of FA: adaptive user interface, high level of information security to ensure the safety

of user data, notification and reminder services for upcoming payments, online chat for customer support, integration with the maximum number of banks for fast transactions, payment gateway for digital payments and transfers. One of the most popular languages for fintech development is Python. For example, the popular Robinhood trading app uses Python and Django.

Conclusion

The rapid development of FA offers users greater control over their financial decisions. Applications increase the accessibility of financial services and the overall level of financial literacy, regardless of economic status or geographical location. Fintech apps provide innovative solutions for tracking and predicting CR, leading to a rethinking of the personal finance management process. The article emphasizes the importance of fintech in enhancing the financial stability of the population, which plays a crucial role in ensuring the sustainable development of the world's economies.

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